

Commercial Cybersecurity

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Abstract:

Objectives: This study explores how cybersecurity impact trade and its policies since technological development become an essential part of the commerce world. The research explains how cybersecurity can be protected and secure commerce by adopting technological means through multi-layered protection using cybersecurity and to determine the relevance of cyber security in commercial businesses along with the future instance of cyber security and its uses.

Methodology: In this study, we will use the analytical approach and the descriptive approach of cyber security on commercial legislation related to the subject of the study.

Results: This study reached several legal results, mainly focusing on clarifying the importance and necessity of cybersecurity as one of the necessities of the business world, which aims to protect its systems from valuable and sensitive commercial and financial information that companies use in their various operations from crimes of electronic theft, damage, or illegal use, as rapid developments in information technology work to perpetuate security threats, making the negative effects of incidents more harmful. On the other hand, the study found that cybersecurity is still in its infancy and requires intensive legal and practical efforts to improve it and expand its use in commerce, which makes cybersecurity an urgent and complex challenge for institutions in commerce.

Recommendations: This study reached a number of results, the most important of which is the Jordanian legislator's recommendation to make legal amendments to the legislation related to cybersecurity regulating trade and its services so that they are flexible and allow the use of advanced protection methods on a practical scale to achieve the required protection.

Keywords: Cybersecurity, trade, protection, commercial legislation, Data, Strategies

1. Introduction

Cybersecurity encompasses a wide range of security issues, from trade in the economic sphere to national security, and a comprehensive treatment of cybersecurity will draw on international relations, security studies, and theory in strategic studies. Commercial cybersecurity is defined as the activities involved in the protection of the commercial enterprise in the cyberspace domain through the development or deployment of information technologies with the objective of achieving security. This is a broad definition, the scope of which can be narrowed down to the areas that directly impact cyber protection of the commercial entity, its data, and its IT infrastructure. This essay will focus on those areas, leaving the treatment of cybersecurity issues with a wider scope to other published works.¹

Measures for protecting the commercial world from cybersecurity threats are in their infancy and, although broad agreement exists on the need for improved cybersecurity, there is little understanding of what this might entail or specific pathways proposed to achieve it. Cyberspace security issues have often been addressed in isolation from the broader context of security, resulting in missed opportunities to learn from security practices in the physical world.²

Cybersecurity is an urgent and complex challenge for organizations, especially in the commercial world. Rapid developments in information technology perpetuate security threats, and the negative effects of security incidents have become more damaging. Malicious hackers are well organized and gain commercial benefit from their hacking activity, using increasingly sophisticated attack methods. They often target businesses that manage large financial transactions, personal identifiable information, and other valuable data.

2. Commercial Cybersecurity concept

In a time where data is key to competitiveness, data loss can be catastrophic. In extreme cases, irreversible data corruption or destruction can put an organization out of business. The implications of data loss are extreme and they serve as a reminder that data security is an essential component to modern business.

Data theft can lead to detrimental damages to an organization. It is not uncommon for stolen data to be abused and the damage caused can be irreversible. As seen in the modern age of technology, information about individuals is often stored in varying databases. Personal data about employees and customers is subject to abuse if accessed by the wrong people. This can lead to identity theft and personal financial loss. The individuals whose data has been stolen may hold the organization accountable for the loss and thus sever business relations. In the worst-case scenario, an organization may face legal action for data loss if it has failed to meet data protection laws.³

In recent years, the security of data has become a significant issue for both organizations and individuals. There have been frequent reports of unauthorized access to data and data misuse. Organizations rely on data to effectively compete in the business environment. Commercial organizations use data to reach target markets or introduce new business strategies. These organizations are often targets for data theft. The data they hold can be extremely valuable and sensitive, subjecting it to theft and misuse by competitors and criminals.

Data is valuable information that is processed and utilized by a computer. It is a varied and complex utility that is used in daily life. It is important to consider the increasing connectivity between systems and users. Data integrity and security are pressing issues for contemporary organizations.⁴

2.1. Protecting the commercial Data

Advantages of cyber security: Finance and data are usually tied together; as one progresses, the other follows. This has both positive and negative connotations. Recent sociological trends have shown that the majority of a developed nation's population will spend the entirety of its disposable income and then some, hence monetary trends often appear synonymous with activity. This is a key concept, as data has quite the same relationship with

activity. Most often when data is said to be lost, it is not randomly deleted. It is actually destroyed or stolen through some form of activity initiated by an outside party. An evaluation of the cost of data breach in a study conducted by the Ponemon Institute in March of 2008 on behalf of PGP Corporation indicated that the average cost of a data breach incident in the United States was \$202 per customer record. This is monumental when one realizes the amount of data that any single record could entail in a modern database. Now multiply that by the number of data breaches mentioned previously. The numbers are staggering and paint a very bleak picture for the state of data security.⁵

When thinking of "data," what comes to mind? In this day and age, this word has come to represent more to humanity than mere facts and figures. Data is the embodiment of the information we pass back and forth, and it is the lifeblood of service in the information age. Think of it, when doing anything from browsing the internet to managing finances to communicating with others, every action brings about a piece of data. As data is the sum of these actions, it holds a large amount of information about the user - and this is what makes it so valuable. All entities, be they persons or large organizations, utilize data in some form to make their decisions. This is what makes the prospect of losing this information a frightening one. In its composition of Version 2.0 of the Dataloss DB, the Open Security Foundation noted that there were over 50 million reported data losses in the period from 2008-2009. Of this astonishing number, there are records for numerous corporations and government entities losing massive amounts of data. A few famous examples of this include the Heartland Payment Systems data breach resulting in over 130 million credit and debit card numbers stolen and the Veterans Affairs laptop theft involving the personal information of over 26 million veterans. The costs of these breaches can be absolutely devastating to an entity.

2.2. Preventing Financial Losses

If sensitive data (corporate or client information) is lost and that loss is detected by cyber criminals great and small who see an opportunity to exploit it to make financial gain – the result can be truly catastrophic. It is common in the aftermath of a data loss incident to focus all attention on how the breach was allowed to occur and what should have been done to prevent it. Little thought is given to the specific financial implications but they can be more far-reaching than one might imagine. One of the clear effects of data loss is often non-compliance with data protection legislation or regulations. This can result in fines or legal action and can take a variety of forms depending on the legislation that has been infringed. An often underestimated impact of a security breach, particularly on the theft of intellectual property, is the time delay between the incident occurring and it being detected by the victim organization. Normally the breach is not detected until the victim organization suffers further problems or there is a second related security incident. In the case of an incident involving sabotage, the criminal may lay silent for a long period of time (perhaps even years), increasing the damage caused. This can result in a claim on insurance policies to cover the loss, though it should be noted that many policies do not cover intellectual property.⁶

2.3. Maintaining commercial Reputation

Public perception of a company is an important factor to consider in any industry. It is essential for organizations to differentiate themselves from their competitors, a task which can be difficult if their reputation is damaged by a security breach. With so many data security companies on the market, any form of security breach for a company working in IT or security solutions can be devastating. The same applies to the financial industry; data theft can be particularly damaging to a company that is trying to convey an image of stability and reliability. For these companies, damage limitation through prevention of data breaches is of utmost importance.⁷

In business, reputations that have taken years of hard work to develop can be destroyed in a matter of minutes following a security breach. While the immediate results of a security breach may not be severe in terms of stolen assets, the long-term effects on the business can sometimes be critical. Customers will lose trust in a company that allows their details to be compromised, and this is a costly process to try and win back their confidence. Without a strong customer base, many companies cannot hope to survive, and the loss of data

through insecure practices can put the future of the business at risk. Given the potential losses, it is clear to see why data security plays a critical role in business continuity and should not be overlooked.⁸

3. Emerging Trends in Commercial Cybersecurity

Unfortunately, there is also a dark side to AI and cybersecurity. Hackers can use machine learning to enhance the precision and effectiveness of attacks. They are able to do this by utilizing the same techniques cybersecurity teams use such as data analysis, intelligent algorithms, and automation. One of the reasons AI has been so effective at improving cybersecurity is because it has lightened the workload for IT security teams by taking care of simple tasks. By using machine learning, hackers can identify and exploit security gaps faster than cybersecurity teams can patch them. This may result in an arms race of machine learning between hackers and cybersecurity.

AI has the potential to greatly enhance cybersecurity. A study by Webroot found that companies who use machine learning technology in their cybersecurity platforms reduced security threats by 11% in the last year. Machine learning is a subset of AI that provides computers with the ability to learn without being explicitly programmed. One of the ways machine learning can do this is by identifying and learning the behavior of certain files. If any abnormality is detected, the program will generate an alert. An example of this is an AI recently developed by MIT that can predict 85% of cyber attacks. This allows for a preventative response to be taken rather than a reactive one.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has been a topic of interest for many years. The concept of a computer that can learn and adapt to new situations without programming changes is very appealing. In the last few years, AI has become less of a science fiction topic and more of a reality with corporations such as Google, Facebook, IBM, and Microsoft making large investments into AI.

3.1. Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning

Multiple responses to the above threats have been made to further increase cybersecurity. For example, certain companies such as OpenAI, a cyber research firm, have proposed building AI bots to act as cyber defenders. Their principle being that "the best way to defend against AI is with more AI". This idea has led to OpenAI creating a prototype known as 'CyberSquirrel1', a modified version of a game simulation. The prototype's purpose will be to act as an AI defender against a variety of AI attackers attempting to cause damage to power grids. The game aims to simulate as closely as possible real-world cyber warfare, with sectors likely to employ cyber attacks against infrastructure able to use the game as a training tool. Another method proposed by researchers from the University of Michigan is to build AI that actually hacks networks with the intention of highlighting vulnerabilities to human defenders. With the same idea, the team has built a prototype bot called 'MAYHEM'. Although these responses give an indication of the direction future cybersecurity might take, it is still unclear how much it will help prevent attacks from AI. The concern being a potential AI arms race with both attackers and defenders continuously developing higher-level AI in an attempt to outsmart the other.

While scholars, researchers, and industry analysts have predicted AI and ML as cyber defenders, cyber attackers are also using AI and ML to launch more sophisticated attacks. Due to AI and ML abilities to learn and create new algorithms, both can be very efficient in finding vulnerabilities in systems and can be trained to exploit these vulnerabilities. With the Sophia bot (AI) created by the University of Luxembourg, it was able to bypass non-player characters (NPCs) and avoid detection from human players when carrying out its attacks in the game Unreal Tournament. This research gives a demonstration of how advanced AI bots can "learn" to find and exploit vulnerabilities while avoiding detection much like a human attacker. With the same principles, AI and ML can also be used to prevent cyber attacks and increase cybersecurity. An example of which would be an intrusion detection system (IDS) using AI to monitor network traffic and detect any unusual patterns with the ability to then create its own algorithms to prevent these attacks. The efficacy of IDS systems designs using AI and ML was trialed in research by Hayajneh et al., where they tested the performance of AI-enhanced IDS

against normal IDS, with results showing a significant increase in accuracy of the AI IDS in detecting and preventing cyber attacks from reaching the network.⁹

3.2. Cloud Security

Back in 2013, the Australian Signals Directorate (ASD) released strategies to mitigate targeted cyber intrusions (also known as the ASD Top 35 Mitigation Strategies) with the top four strategies showing that 85% of breaches could be avoided by proactively implementing these four strategies. Compare this to the release of the cloud computing consumer-centric self-assessment, where someone with a credit card and an internet connection can start provisioning computing resources. Spin up a virtual computer in Brazil, an SQL database in Japan, or a scalable cluster of Linux web servers in London at will, with just a few mouse clicks... The ease of use and flexibility that a cloud environment offers has now complicated the effort for an organization to know where their data is stored and what legislation or compliance requirements there are on the storage and use of that data. Add in the shared responsibility model of security, which differs between cloud service providers, and it's clear that understanding the best way to secure your data within a cloud environment is not a simple task.¹⁰

Adoption of cloud technologies in almost every area of our professional and personal life is happening more rapidly than anticipated. According to Forbes, recently 83% of enterprise workloads are in the cloud and by 2020, 41% of workloads will be processed using public cloud platforms. Whether cloud storage, message platforms, CRMs or ERPs, these technologies offer cost-effective and flexible solutions to businesses of all sizes. However, it is not without increased cybersecurity risk, largely due to the data no longer being stored with the owner organization.¹¹

3.3 Blockchain Technology for Data Protection

However, the installation of blockchain poses a number of issues. The method causes transparency and gives the user less privacy to their own information. In addition to this, the difficulty of implementing the technology into an existing system is a large barrier to overcome. Despite this, current research suggests that blockchain technology would be a secure way of international data transfer between third parties. This suggests that the potential implementation of blockchain would be an effective way to secure data in the future and diminish the growing concerns of cyber threats to data security.

Blockchain technology has seen its most visible implementation in cryptocurrency, but due to its improved security of data transfer, it has been suggested as a viable technology for improving data protection within the cybersecurity industry. Blockchain is built around the concept of distributed ledgers. Two parties have access to the same documentation in real time, and this documentation can be updated at any time. This method allows information to be transferred in a safe and secure manner, as the documentation is always kept up to date and can be easily restored to previous iterations. The concept is a natural fit for the cybersecurity industry. The nature of the technology makes cyber attacks very difficult, as the information is likely spread over thousands of documents and any changes to data would be immediately apparent. In addition to this, data recovery is much easier when compared to traditional backup storage.¹²

4. Strategies for Commercial Cybersecurity

An effective approach to commercial cybersecurity will ultimately reduce risk to employees, customers, suppliers, and partners and enable a business to function most effectively, free from the threat of attack. To this end, a robust cyber strategy should be aligned with the overall business strategy and should be revisited regularly. However, it is also important to recognize that the cyber threat is constantly evolving, and so the strategy should be sufficiently flexible to adapt to emerging threats. The 2013 cyber-attack on retailer Target, which resulted in the theft of 40 million credit card details, is a good example of the need to realign business and security strategy. In the aftermath of the attack, it was revealed that warnings from Target's security systems were ignored, and the company had failed to act on them. Had the warnings been acted upon, the attack might have been prevented. Finally, the strategy should balance the costs of protection with the benefits. Not all data has equal value or requires the same level of protection, so the most cost-effective strategy will be one that focuses protection on the most valuable data.

4.1. Implementing Strong Access Controls

With plenty of access control methods for information and resources, quality security-critical but suboptimal ways of achieving security can be avoided by employing increasingly specific and higher-level security requirements, plans, and policies for access controls.

At the systems level, an access control mechanism can be enforced through role-based access control (RBAC) and access control lists (ACL). These are two fundamental concepts that have been around for some time and do much to systematize the enforcement of access controls at the level of the file system in RBAC or for general network resources with ACLs. ACLs reflect positively documented recommendations that access to system objects be restricted to processes functioning on behalf of a given user or to deny access by default and permit access on the basis of some specific condition.

It is wise to restrict access to resources and information to the greatest extent possible. Consider using the principle of least privilege, which requires that an individual component or system process is not granted any more access privilege than is necessary to perform the intended function. This minimizes the potential damage that can be done through human error. Always ensure that inactive access rights are removed or modified if the continuance of access is no longer necessary. Finally, an access control system should be monitored, and it should be regularly tested. Any irregularities or attempts to breach security should be logged and investigated.¹

Given the risks that access control measures are designed to address, controlling the flow of information and physical access to an information system in order to prevent any unauthorized access, analyze, or disclose information, secure access control is a cornerstone of information security. Access controls are subject to much interpretation, and this is another area where we recommend using a framework to govern policy, resource, and the allocation of access rights. However, some general advice relevant to all access controls can be given.

4.2. Regular Security Audits and Updates

Regular security audits and updates are important for maintaining a strong cybersecurity posture. An audit is a systematic evaluation of an organization's security policy and procedures. The key to an effective audit is to evaluate how well the organization's security policy is matched with reality. This task is difficult, as it is often the case that written policy is not adhered to in practice. Regular system updates are necessary for eliminating the vulnerabilities that threaten the security of an IT system. It is generally the case that the more widely used a piece of software, the more likely it is that someone will discover a vulnerability in it. Any newly discovered vulnerability represents a new security hole that can potentially be exploited. Updates seek to rectify these issues in a proactive manner, before they can be exploited. Regular audits and updates are crucial for preventing attack, as older vulnerabilities are a prime target for malicious individuals. By continually assessing the security posture

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of an organization and eliminating known vulnerabilities, it is possible to drastically reduce the chances of a security breach.¹³

4.3. Incident Response and Recovery Plans

Redundant systems are also very useful in recovering from a cyber-attack. If a system is compromised, having a backup system can limit the damage that is done. There are several types of redundant systems. Disk imaging involves making an exact copy of a computer's hard drive. If the original drive is corrupted, it can be quickly swapped with the backup drive. Clustering involves having two or more computers working on a similar task. If one is compromised, the others can pick up the slack. This also works with network systems. If a server is compromised, another server can quickly take its place to prevent much downtime.

In the commercial world, cyber-attacks can cause chaotic and damaging results. If a company can prevent an attack from happening, they can save valuable resources. One way of preventing attacks is to develop a strong incident response plan. This plan allows the company to identify an attack in progress and prevent it from causing too much damage. There are six steps involved in developing and maintaining an incident response plan. The first step is to prepare the organization for an incident. This step involves getting management support for the plan, developing the plan itself, and selecting a team to carry out the plan. The next step is to identify an attack if or when one is in progress. This can sometimes be difficult as the attack could come in the form of slight data corruption or a massive and obvious data theft. Once the attack is identified, the next step is to contain the damage that has been done. This usually involves disconnecting affected systems and/or creating backup systems to keep the company operational. The fourth step is to repair the damage that was done. This can be a long and costly process, especially if data was destroyed. The fifth step is to return to normal operations. Depending on the severity of the attack, this could take a long time and require checking the system for any remaining problems. The final step is to review the incident. This is useful in identifying what was done right and wrong in the handling of the incident and using that information to improve the response plan for the future.¹⁴

5. Conclusion

The study we conducted entitled “Commercial Cybersecurity” is considered one of the topics that has gained great popularity among trade circles and the bodies regulating cybersecurity in Jordan and internationally because of its great importance, which has been exacerbated by the technological development that has accompanied the development of trade and its various businesses and systems around the world. On the one hand, and the multiplicity of cyber security organizations on the other. We have reached several conclusions and recommendations as follows.

5.1 Results

- Cybersecurity plays a critical role in protecting online commercial transactions, sensitive customer information, secure financial transactions, preserving trust and continued growth of e-commerce.
- As the retail paradigm shifts increasingly toward online shopping, cybersecurity becomes a pivotal aspect that can make or break an e-commerce business.
- The Growing Importance of Cybersecurity for commercial Businesses With the increasing reliance on technology and the internet since cyber threats are becoming more sophisticated and frequent, posing a significant risk to commercial of all types and ways.

5.2 recommendation

- Establishing a technological security legal system that includes provisions that must be applied specifically to commerce and electronic commerce

- Creating national legislation that establishes explicit and clear legal provisions that define the nature of legal or criminal liability for cybersecurity crimes and commercial protection frameworks.
- Identifying an official body regarding the implementation of cybersecurity in businesses, following up and documenting it

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